

Text Extraction from Image using Python

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ABSTRACT

With so much of our lives computerized, it is vitally important that machines and humans can understand one another and pass information back and forth. Mostly computers have things their way we have to & talk to them through relatively crude devices such as keyboards and mice so they can figure out what we want them to do. However, when it comes to processing more human kinds of information, like an old-fashioned printed book or a letter scribbled with a fountain pen, computers have to work much harder. That is where optical character recognition (OCR) comes in. Here we process the image, where we apply various pre-processing techniques like desk wing, binarization etc. and algorithms like Tesseract to recognize the characters and give us the final document.

Keywords: *Open CV- Python; Image Processing; Text Extraction; Image threshold; Virtual Image*

I. INTRODUCTION

Text data present in images contain useful information for automatic annotation, indexing, and structuring of images. Extraction of this information involves detection, localization, tracking, extraction, enhancement, and recognition of the text from a given image. However, variations of text due to differences in size, style, orientation, and alignment, as well as low image contrast and complex background make the problem of automatic text extraction extremely

challenging. While comprehensive surveys of related problems such as face detection, document analysis, and image indexing can be found, the problem of text information extraction is not well surveyed. A large number of techniques have been proposed to address this problem, and the purpose of this paper is to classify and review these algorithms, discuss benchmark data and performance evaluation, and to point out promising directions for future research.

Content-based image indexing refers to the process of attaching labels to images based on their content. Image content can be divided into two main categories: perceptual content and semantic content. Perceptual content includes attributes such as color, intensity, shape, texture, and their temporal changes, whereas semantic content means objects, events, and their relations. A number of studies on the use of relatively low-level perceptual content for image and video indexing have already been reported. Studies on semantic image content in the form of text, face, vehicle, and human action have also attracted some recent interest. Among them, text within an image is of particular interest as

- It is very useful for describing the contents of an image;
- It can be easily extracted compared to other semantic contents, and
- It enables applications such as keyword-based image search, automatic video logging, and text-based image indexing.

II. TEXT IN IMAGES

A variety of approaches to text information extraction (TIE) from images have been proposed for specific applications including page segmentation, address block location, license plate location, and content-based image indexing.

Fig. 1: Grayscale document images

Fig. 2: Multi-color document images

Fig. 3: Images with caption text

Fig. 4: Scene text images

Text in images can exhibit many variations with respect to the properties like geometry, color, motion, edge and compression.

Table 1: Properties of text in images

Properties		Variants or sub-classes
Geometry	Size	Regularity in size of text
	Alignment	Horizontal/vertical
		Straight line with skew (implies vertical direction)
		Curves
Inter-character distance	3D perspective distortion	
Colour	Aggregation of characters with uniform distance	
	Colour	Gray Colour (monochrome, polychrome)
Motion	Static	
	Linear Movement	
	2D rigid constrained movement	
	3D rigid constrained movement	
	Free Movement	
Edge	Strong edges (contrast) at text boundaries	
Compression	Un-compressed image	
	JPEG, MPEG-compressed image	

The problem of Text Information Extraction TIE system receives an input in the form of a still image or a sequence of images. The images can be in gray scale or color, compressed or un-compressed, and the text in the images may or may not move. The TIE problem can be divided into the following sub-problems: (i) detection, (ii) localization, (iii) tracking, (iv) extraction and enhancement (v) Optical Character recognition (OCR).

III. IMAGE THRESHOLDING

A. Threshold Binary

Fig.5: Threshold Binary

This thresholding operation can be expressed as:

$$dst(x, y) = \begin{cases} \text{maxVal} & \text{if } src(x, y) > \text{thresh} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

So, if the intensity of the pixel $src(x, y)$ is higher than $thresh$, then the new pixel intensity is set to a $MaxVal$. Otherwise, the pixels are set to 0 .

B. Threshold Binary, Inverted

Fig. 5: Threshold Binary, Inverted

This thresholding operation can be expressed as:

$$dst(x, y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } src(x, y) > \text{thresh} \\ \text{maxVal} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

If the intensity of the pixel $src(x, y)$ is higher than $thresh$, then the new pixel intensity is set to a 0 . Otherwise, it is set to $MaxVal$.

C. Truncate

Fig. 6: Truncate

This thresholding operation can be expressed as:

$$dst(x, y) = \begin{cases} \text{threshold} & \text{if } src(x, y) > \text{thresh} \\ src(x, y) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The maximum intensity value for the pixels is $thresh$, if $src(x, y)$ is greater, then its value is *truncated*. See figure below:

D. Threshold to Zero

Fig. 7: Threshold to Zero

This operation can be expressed as:

$$dst(x, y) = \begin{cases} src(x, y) & \text{if } src(x, y) > \text{thresh} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

If $thresh$ is lower than $thresh$, the new pixel value will be set to 0 .

E. Threshold to Zero, Inverted

Fig. 8: Threshold to Zero, Inverted

This operation can be expressed as:

$$dst(x, y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } src(x, y) > \text{thresh} \\ src(x, y) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

If $thresh$ is greater than $thresh$, the new pixel value will be set to 0 .

F. Simple Thresholding

If pixel value is greater than a threshold value, it is assigned one value (may be white), else it is assigned another value (may be black). The function used is `cv2.threshold`. First argument is the source image, which **should be a grayscale image**. Second argument is the threshold value which is used to classify the pixel values. Third argument is the `maxVal` which represents the value to be given if pixel value is more than (sometimes less than) the threshold value. OpenCV provides different styles of thresholding and it is decided by the fourth parameter of the function. Different types are:

- `cv2.THRESH_BINARY`
- `cv2.THRESH_BINARY_INV`

- cv2.THRESH_TRUNC
- cv2.THRESH_TOZERO
- cv2.THRESH_TOZERO_INV

Two outputs are obtained. First one is a **retval** . Second output is our **thresholded image**.

Fig. 9: Image Describing outputs of different Thresholding techniques

IV. PYTHON ANYWHERE

Python Anywhere is an online Integrated Development Environment (IDE) and Web hosting service based on the Python programming language. It provides in browser access to server-based Python and Bash Command-line interfaces, along with a code editor with Syntax highlighting. One striking different between Python Anywhere and the usual Python Cloud Computing solution that we know of, is that you can totally work on it online using internet browser in developing your Python application. With this, you can bypass the usual delicacies on preparing a local workstation that meet cloud hosting service environment requirement and directly work inside your browser that connected to many consoles provided by Python anywhere, such as : Bash, Python/iPython 2.6/2.7/3.3 and MySQL.

This provides a step-by-step guide on how to deploy your Django applications. The service provides in-browser access to the server-based Python and Bash command line interfaces, meaning you can interact with Python Anywhere's servers just like you would with a regular terminal instance on your own computer. Currently, Python Anywhere are offering a free account which sets you up with an adequate amount of storage space and CPU time to get a Django application up and running.

A. Creating a Python Anywhere Account

First sign up for a Beginner Python Anywhere account. If your application takes off and becomes popular, you can always upgrade your account at a later stage to gain more storage space and CPU time along with a number of other benefits (like hosting specific domains and ssh abilities).

Once your account has been created, you will have your own little slice of the World Wide Web at <http://<username>.pythonanywhere.com>, where <username> is your Python Anywhere username. It is from this URL that your hosted application will be available from.

B. The Python Anywhere Web Interface

The Python Anywhere web interface contains a *dashboard*, which in turn provides a series of tabs allowing you to manage your application. The tabs as illustrated in Fig. 10 include:

- a *consoles* tab, allowing you to create and interact with Python and Bash console instances;
- a *files* tab, which allows you to upload to and organize files within your disk quota;
- a *web* tab, allowing you to configure settings for your hosted web application;
- a *schedule* tab, allowing you to setup tasks to be executed at particular times; and
- a *databases* tab, which allows you to configure a MySQL instance for your applications should you require it.

Of the five tabs provided, we'll be working primarily with the *consoles* and *web* tabs. The Python Anywhere help pages provide a series of detailed explanations on how to use the other tabs.

Fig. 10: The Python Anywhere dashboard, showing the *Consoles* tab.

C. Python Anywhere to upload the image

Fig. 11: Python Anywhere IDE to upload image

In the Python Anywhere IDE, the user can upload the image from which he or she wishes to extract the text. After logging into Python Anywhere account, a user has to go to the working directory where one can find “Upload a File” option. Clicking on it lets user chose the desired image and then uploads it to Python Anywhere cloud.

D. The Bash Console

Fig. 12: Finding Bash Console in Python Anywhere

Python Anywhere allows a user to have two consoles for a free trial. On upgrading the account, a user can increase this number. To run the python files one must open the bash console.

Fig. 13: Running Files in Bash Console

Here we specify the file we wish to run. Python is the keyword to specify that we are running a python file and testest.py is the file name.

E. Result File

Fig. 14: Text files containing extracted text

The text extracted from the images is pipelined to a text file where the user can view, edit and modify its contents. User can thus save the obtained text file and download it from Python Anywhere.

V. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

A. System Architecture

The entire process can be depicted using these basic steps:

Fig. 15: Workflow in the system

The three basic steps involved in this process are detection, enhancement and extraction. This diagram defines the structure of the system.

Fig. 16: Detailed Architecture of system

VI. Test cases

Table 2: Test Cases

S. No	Test Case	Expected Result	Actual	Result
1	Image with plain Text and plain background	Text extracted	Text extracted	Passed
2	Image with luminance	Text extracted	Text extracted	Passed
3	Tabular data which contains the rows and columns	Text extracted	Text extracted	Passed
4	Letter head	Text extracted	Text extracted	Passed
5	Bond paper with the text content which is in colour	Text extracted	Text extracted	Passed
6	Signboard containing text	Text extracted	Text extracted	Passed
7	Text with varying font size	Text extracted	Text extracted	Passed
8	Handwritten text	Text extracted		Partially passed
9	Image with high text data of low details	Text extracted	Text extracted	Failed

10	Complex background image with tilted text containing mixed colours	Text extracted	Text extracted	Failed
11	Label on water bottle	Text extracted	Text extracted	Failed

Below are the results of few test cases performed. The original image and the extracted text are shown below.

A. Example 1:

Fig.17: Image

Fig. 18: Image with plain background

B. Example 2:

Fig. 19: Bond Paper

Fig. 20: Bond Paper with plain background

C. Example 3:

Fig. 21: Hand writing Image

Fig. 22: Image with plain background

D. Example 4:

Fig. 23: Image with high text data of low details

Fig. 24: Image with high text data of low details

E. Example 5:

Fig. 25: Complex background image with tilted text containing mixed colors

Fig. 25: Complex background image with tilted text containing mixed colors with plain background

CONCLUSION

Even though a large number of algorithms have been proposed in the literature, no single method can provide satisfactory performance in all the applications due to the large variations in character font, size, texture, color, etc. Through this paper we are in the stream of deriving the satisfactory results by enhancing the input by fine tuning the image and deriving the optimum levels of accuracy from TESSERACT.

FUTURE SCOPE

With machine learning algorithms constantly being developed and improved, massive amounts of computational power becoming readily available both locally and on the cloud, and unfathomable amounts of data can be extracted not only in the domain of image but also in terms of scene, video frames and scrolling types of data.

REFERENCES

- 1) M. Flickner, H. Sawney et al., Query by Image and Video Content: The QBIC System, IEEE Computer 28 (9) (1995) 23-32.
- 2) J. Zhang, Y. Gong, S. W. Smoliar, and S. Y. Tan, Automatic Parsing of News Video, Proc. of IEEE Conference on Multimedia Computing and Systems, 1994, pp. 45-54.
- 3) M. H. Yang, D. J. Kriegman, and N. Ahuja, Detecting faces in Images: A Survey, IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, 24 (1) (2002) 34-58.
- 4) Y. Cui and Q. Huang, Character Extraction of License Plates from Video, Proc. of IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 1997, pp. 502–507.
- 5) C. Colombo, A. D. Bimbo, and P. Pala, Semantics in Visual Information Retrieval, IEEE Multimedia, 6 (3) (1999) 38-53.
- 6) T. Sato, T. Kanade, E. K. Hughes, and M. A. Smith, Video OCR for Digital News Archive, Proc. of IEEE Workshop on Content based Access of Image and Video Databases, 1998, pp. 52-60.
- 7) Atsuo Yoshitaka and Tadao Ichikawa, A Survey on Content-based Retrieval for Multimedia Databases, IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering, 11(1999) 81-93.
- 8) W. Qi, L. Gu, H. Jiang, X. Chen, and H. Zhang, Integrating Visual, Audio, and Text Analysis for News Video, Proc. of IEEE International Conference on Image Processing, 2000, pp. 10-13.
- 9) D. Wactlar, T. Kanade, M. A. Smith, and S. M. Stevens, Intelligent Access to Digital Video: The Informedia Project, IEEE Computer, 29 (5) (1996) 46-52.
- 10) H. Rein-Lien, M. Abdel-Mottaleb, A. K. Jain, Face Detection in Color Images, IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, 24 (5) (2002) 696-706.